

Analysing Consumer Behaviour and Demand Dynamics of Poultry Based Fast Food in Faisalabad, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: Fast food consumption among young people is growing rapidly worldwide, driven by convenience, affordability, and marketing strategies. This has led to notable dietary changes in South Asia, including Pakistan. This study uses demand theory and analysing participant survey data to understand the factors influencing fast food consumption in Faisalabad, a city experiencing rapid urbanization. The analysis reveals that younger, educated, and higher-income individuals are the primary consumers of fast food. Food quality plays a significant role in driving spending, while price sensitivity is relatively low. For example, a 1% increase in price results in only a 0.14% decrease in consumption. On the other hand, income elasticity shows that a 1% increase in income leads to a 15.88% rise in consumption. The study also highlights how popular fast food items like burgers, pizza, and shawarma have substitutive and complementary relationships. These findings offer businesses, policymakers, and health experts valuable insights to address fast-food trends' social, economic, and health effects.

KEYWORDS: Consumer Behaviour, Demand analysis, Fast food, Income elasticity, Price elasticity

INTRODUCTION

Poultry farms are crucial for global food security and economic stability while creating employment opportunities worldwide. High-quality protein from poultry farms is a primary nutritional source, which is significant for developing countries. The food industry depends heavily on poultry farming to provide cost-effective protein sources for consumers. The system provides essential nutrition to areas where people lack access to various food types. We obtain a substantial portion of our food supply through poultry farming, which provides affordable protein sources for people worldwide. This approach provides essential nutrition supply to areas where people face restricted food variety availability Al-Khalafah & Al-Nasser (2022). According to an economic survey of Pakistan, the Pakistani poultry industry maintains its position as one of the country's largest and most dynamic economic sectors by contributing about 1.5 per cent to Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The poultry industry is Pakistan's second-largest economic sector behind textiles, displaying continuous growth patterns. The industry forecast shows it will generate 1.5 million new employment opportunities in future years. Pakistan ranks as the 11th largest chicken producer worldwide with annual production of 48.83 million layer chickens, 1.02 billion broilers, and 11.8 million breeding stocks.

Poultry based Fast food consumption among youth is rising due to convenience, affordability, and strong marketing. Social media trends and peer influence also drive demand. The global fast food market was USD 862.05 Billion in 2020 and is expected to reach USD 1,467.04 Billion in 2028 at a Compound Annual Growth Rate of 6.05 (Fortune Business Insights, 2022). South Asia is experiencing a nutrition transition, shifting from a traditional diet high in carbohydrates and low in fats to one higher in saturated fats, sugars, and salt. This change is driven by economic growth and increased disposable income (Bishwajit, 2015). Fast food is considered ultra-processed, high-energy food that is easy and quick to prepare. It is typically served as a quick meal from restaurants or snack shops for dining in or takeout (Lin & Frazao, 1997). While fast food is gaining popularity across all age groups, young adults remain the primary consumers globally (Mathur & Patodiya, 2016). Additionally, eating out has become a trendy habit among

young adults, contributing to a rise in the frequency of fast food consumption. This shift is often influenced by convenience, social factors, and the growing availability of fast food options (Janssen et al., 2017). The fast-food industry in Pakistan is the second-largest food sector, contributing 27% to production and 16% to employment. It serves 169 million consumers and has over 1,000 food processing enterprises (Akhtar, 2013).

New trends in improving the food expenditure ratios of Pakistan within the last three decades call for extensive and more concentrated future research on increasing trends in the consumption behavior of the populace. Newspaper and magazine articles alone prove that a more significant portion of the food budget for households goes to eating out, especially to fast foods and restaurants. This change can be said to have brought a dramatic shift in dietary trends due to the growth of urban centers and their attendant changes, as well as the change in the economic status of societies. The latest trend in fast food, particularly with the young generation, compels us to know why this is the trend since it has many impacts on health, food security, and the economy. Therefore, it is imperative to analyze these changes to help guide policy-making, business and health strategies, and organizational practices.

This research is based on demand theory as a branch of microeconomic theory emphasizing consumer behavior about food. In line with economic theory, other factors affect the expenditure incurred on food, such as income level, prices of food products, preference, and availability of substitutes. Appreciation of how these variables work in this context to build demand for fast foods begins with understanding the following areas of economics (M. Gostkowski, 2018). The elasticity of income and price gives an understanding of how the change in these factors affects demand for products, which will be deemed significant in the fast-food market segment.

Several studies have investigated the impact of food choices and marketing on health outcomes. The Fast food industry has witnessed tremendous growth in the global markets due to push factors that change consumers' eating habits. Based on findings by Jang and Mattila (2005), customers rank value, food quality, convenience, and entertainment as the most influential factors in fast food consumption, especially for impulse products. Korkmaz (2005) divided that according to ethnic hamburger and non-hamburger segments, where McDonald's and KFC belong to the non-hamburger segment. Riaz et al. (2006) and Shaikh & Rehman (2010) also revealed that KFC's local rival has been able to challenge multinationals since they adopted appropriate economic prices of meals, which the local people normally accept about their economic stature. This factor also refers to the penetration and acceptability of this form of food consumption and the culture of fast foods as they form part of many societies' way of life. However, concerns have been raised over the consumption of fast foods has effects on the health status of people, especially children and teenagers, as highlighted by Andreyeva et al. 2011 and Zahedi et al., 2014 who pointed out that the consumption of fast foods has led to increased cases of obesity and mental issues. In addition, appealing food promotion that aims at children, like kids' meals and toys, presents evidence of increasing consumption of unhealthy foods (Vachaspati et al., 2015). Brunello et al. (2014) found that school fruit schemes replacing junk food with fruits and vegetables promoted healthier eating habits among schoolchildren, with a decline in supermarket snack sales in participating schools. Payab et al. (2014) linked junk food consumption to obesity and hypertension in Iranian children and advocated for higher taxes and restrictions on junk food ads. Baig and Saeed (2012) traced the evolution of fast food in Pakistan, marking the 1997 introduction of Pizza Hut as the start of a fast food revolution. Yu (2012) found that most mothers believed TV food ads negatively influenced their children's food choices, calling for stricter regulations. Rojas et al. (2013) identified factors like rural living, convenience, and health awareness influencing fast food consumption, recommending policies to promote healthier eating. Yahya et al. (2013) noted that modern lifestyles emphasizing convenience contributed to higher fast food demand and spending, with significant health implications. Alviola et al. (2014) discovered that fast food outlets near schools were linked to higher obesity rates in Arkansas, advocating for healthier school snacks and education. The fast-food industry in Pakistan is emerging, with existing literature on the sector. However, there is a lack of focus on Faisalabad, which is experiencing significant demographic and socioeconomic changes. In the context of demand for fast food, previous literature has examined customer preference within large national settings. However, more detailed analyses of what drives consumers in Faisalabad have not undergone extensive discussion. In addition, more research is required to understand factors that may include income levels, pricing strategy, and socio-cultural factors influencing consumers in this new market. This research seeks to fill these gaps by extending the knowledge on the local processes of fast food consumption and, hence, supporting the existing knowledge on consumers' behaviour in emergent economies.

The main objective of this research is to analyze consumer satisfaction with the Faisalabad fast-food business about potential customer demographic characteristics, their consumption profile, the effect of the price level for fast foods, and the consumer's

income level. The cross-sectional study targeting 150 fast food consumers will help estimate the income and price elasticity of demand to understand the economic and psychological aspects influencing fast food consumption. By so doing, this research will not only advance the empirical knowledge about the demand for fast foods in a developing country, Pakistan, but also present implications to the businesses in the food sector, policymakers, and health care practitioners and workers in a quest to address emerging issues caused by shifting food consumption trends.

METHODS

This research was undertaken in Faisalabad, Pakistan, with a sample size of 150 participants. To check on the relevance and comprehensiveness of the data collection instrument, a pilot test was conducted on 20 people selected from the population on a random basis, which helped in removing those items that were not relevant in the tool in the form of a questionnaire. The primary data were collected using questionnaires administered to the household respondents from October to December 2024 with simple random sampling. The chosen sample size was deemed adequate in the study's time and resource constraints.

This study employed descriptive statistics to summarize the primary variables of the sample, utilizing frequencies and percentages to provide a comprehensive overview of key socio-economic and demographic characteristics. This approach enabled a clearer understanding of the distribution and trends within the sample population, facilitating the interpretation of various factors influencing the study's context.

Multiple linear regressions

Multiple regression was used to determine the factors affecting fast food consumption in Faisalabad, Pakistan.

The multiple regression equation used is as follows:

$$FFC = \beta_0 + \beta_1AGE + \beta_2EDU + \beta_3MI + \beta_4VRF + \beta_5ENV + \beta_6QFF + \beta_7PFF + \mu \quad (1)$$

Where

- FFC = Fast food consumption, monthly expenditure on fast food in Rs/Month
- AGE = Age of the respondents
- EDU = (Education of the respondents)
- MI = (Monthly income of the respondents in Rs/Month)
- VRF = various fast food like burgers, fries, pizza, shawarma, etc.
- EFFR =Environment of the fast food restaurants
- QFF =Quality of the fast food in taste and nutritional
- PFF =Price of fast food in Rs/Month
- μ = Error term

Demand Functions

The demand for different fast-food items, Burgers, Pizza and Shawarma was estimated. The general form of the demand function is specified as:

$$D_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1PB + \beta_2PP + \beta_3PS + \beta_4MIH + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Where:

- D_i =Demand for the ith fast food item (burger, pizza, shawarma).
- PB =Price of burgers.
- PP =Price of pizza.
- PS = Price of shawarma.
- MIH = Monthly income of households.
- $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ =The coefficients to be estimated.
- ϵ =Error term.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 reveals the respondent profile, which is a diverse demographic distribution. Most respondents (71.33%) are aged between 21 and 40, with a nearly equal gender split (49.33% female and 50.67% male). Educationally, most respondents hold undergraduate or higher qualifications (57.71%), reflecting a relatively well-educated sample. Regarding marital status, 62% are married, while

38% are single. Income distribution shows a significant portion (40%) earning below 25,000, while the remaining respondents are distributed across higher income brackets. Fast food expenditure varies considerably, with 47.33% spending less than 1,500 monthly and 22.67% spending over 4,500, indicating diverse consumption patterns within the sample. This profile provides important contextual information for interpreting the findings of the study.

Table 1: Respondent profile

	Profile	Size	Proportion	
Age	< 20	11	7,33	
	21 - 40	107	71,33	
	41 - 60	32	21,33	
Gender	Female	74	49,33	
	Male	76	50,67	
Education	Middle	22	14,57	
	Metric	27	17,88	
	Intermediate	15	9,93	
	Undergraduate	44	29,14	
Masters and above		43	28,57	
	Marital Status	Single	57	38
	Married	93	62	
Monthly Income	< 25000	60	40	
	26000 - 50000	42	28	
	51000 - 75000	38	25,33	
	>75000	10	6,67	
Monthly spending on Fast food	<1500	71	47,33	
	1600-3000	29	19,33	
	3100-4500	16	10,67	
	>4500	34	22,67	

Multiple regression analyses were conducted using SPSS to determine whether the identified factors influence the demand for fast food consumption in Faisalabad. The method of multiple regression analysis, first introduced by Pearson and Lee in 1908, utilizes more than one independent variable to explain the maximum variation in the dependent variable.

Table 4.1: Regression coefficients

Variables	Coefficients	t-value	Significance
Constant	3.111	18.474	0.000
AGE	-0.262	-3.779	0.000
EDU	.203	2.739	0.007
MI	.185	2.724	0.007
VRF	-0.065	-0.868	0.387
ENV	0.070	0.940	0.349

QFF	0.007	0.093	0.026
P	-.122	-1.755	0.081
R square	0.460		
Adjusted R square	0.425		
F	13.230		

The regression analysis in Table 2 shows that the overall model is statistically significant. A negative and statistically significant relationship exists between AGE and fast food expenditure. The negative coefficient suggests that participants of a higher age consume less fast food. This could be because older adults have better and healthier eating habits or better dietary practices and could be less dependent on fast food than young people. (Hong, 2019) conclude that younger people consume more fast food than older individuals, and (Moosburger et al., 2020) show that older adolescents 17 years in Germany are more likely to be high consumers of fast food compared to younger adolescents. Education is significantly positively associated with fast food expenditure. Higher education levels are linked to increased fast food spending. Educated individuals may also be more aware of the variety and quality of fast food options, potentially influencing their consumption patterns. Rössel (2015) indicates that higher education levels correlate with more informed choices regarding food, impacting preferences and promoting healthier consumption patterns. Islam (2021) Concludes that higher education leads to reduced fast food consumption in Indonesia. Fast food expenditure has a positive and significant relationship with monthly income. In general, fast foods usually capture the higher-income earners since they have more disposable income to spend on non-essential goods, so it is expected that people with higher total income would spend a proportionately more significant part of their expenses on fast foods. This result is in line with (Lotfali Agheli and Emamgholipour, 2016) and (Hoffer et al., 2017), who found that income positively relates to fast food consumption. The variety of fast food does not significantly impact fast food expenditure. The insignificance of this variable suggests that the number of fast food options available does not strongly influence spending behavior. Maybe a variety of fast food is less important to consumers when the core factors of taste, price, and convenience dominate their decision-making process. (Parvin, 2022) highlights various factors influencing fast food consumption, including variety, convenience, taste, and availability. The environment of the fast-food restaurant seems to be of little importance. This suggests that the physical surroundings of the restaurant do not significantly influence how much customers spend. Instead, they focus more on quality and the price of the food. This study aligns with Polsky and Garriguet (2023), who found no association between restaurant exposure and food consumption. The quality of fast food has a robust positive relation with expenditure. Food quality in terms of taste and nutritional value, where improvements will trigger increases in fast food consumption. Consumers who perceive fast foods as quality foods are likely to spend more on them, causing an increase in their expenditure. Such a result indicates that food quality is a vital factor affecting fast food consumption. However, they are tasty and the best food that meets the customers’ preferences for health benefits associated with the food. (Skoufias et al., 2011) discuss the role of food quality in household expenditure, showing that as food quality increases, households allocate a more significant share of their budget to higher-quality options, including fast food. There is a negative but statistically insignificant relationship between the price of fast food and fast food expenditure. The negative sign implies that higher prices may slow down consumption, while the marginal analysis suggests that this conclusion is not robust. This result is in line with (Chidinma et al., 2022). A possibility could be that price may not negatively influence expenditure because, in the eyes of some consumers, fast food could have value or be of higher quality than the price makes it to be, especially if it is advertised to be on promotion or on some discounts.

Consumption of Fast Food: Burger, Pizza and Shawarma

Fast Food	Mean Consumption (Per Month)	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Burger	12.56	8.42	4	32
Pizza	6.05	2.66	4	12
Shawarma	11.68	8.47	1	48

Demand estimation of burgers

$$D_{Burger} = 0.587 - 0.084PB + 0.010PP + 0.065PS + 0.010MIH \quad (3)$$

$$R^2 = 0.69 \quad F = 64.450 \quad (Sig = 0.000)$$

Demand estimation shows that burger demand responds strongly to burger prices and substitute food prices while also depending on monthly income. According to the law of demand, when burger prices rise, consumers tend to buy less; when pizza and shawarma prices rise, consumers switch to burgers because these items serve as burger alternatives. The positive link between burger sales and monthly income shows that burgers behave as normal goods because people buy more when their income grows (Andreyeva et al., 2010). The model shows that it explains most of the burger consumption patterns, and its statistical results prove that these factors help predict how much people will buy burgers. The model shows strong results but still leaves some demand patterns unexplained, suggesting other factors like marketing efforts and seasonal trends could affect burger consumption.

Demand estimation of pizza:

$$D_{pizza} = 0.477 + 0.036PB - 0.181PP + 0.094PS + 0.044MIH \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.042 \quad F = 0.770 \quad (Sig = 0.000)$$

Equation 4 demand estimation shows how burgers, pizzas, shawarma, and monthly income prices affect customer choices. The positive burger price effect shows that pizza demand grows when burger prices rise because people tend to consume these items together or prefer them as a package. The negative price coefficient shows how higher pizza prices decrease product demand, which is the law of demand. When shawarma prices rise, customers buy more pizzas because these products are alternatives. People buy more pizzas when their monthly income rises because pizzas act as normal goods (Dean et al., 2020). The model explains that only a tiny part of pizza demand changes because its R-squared value remains low. The model shows that these factors impact pizza demand, yet other elements still affect how people buy pizza. In one study reveals that people prefer traditional pizza instead of frozen pizza and also they prefer organic ingredients in Italy (Vita et al., 2016)

Demand estimation of shawarma:

$$D_{shawarma} = 0.957 + 0.030PB + 0.126PP - 0.018PS + 0.071MIH \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.20 \quad F = 0.646 \quad (Sig = 0.000)$$

The model shows how prices of burgers, pizzas, and shawarma plus monthly income affect customer choices. When burger prices go up, people buy more shawarma. People tend to eat more shawarma when pizza prices increase because these two foods are substitutes. The negative coefficient for shawarma price shows that demand decreases when prices rise because of the law of demand (Andreyeva et al., 2010). People buy more shawarma when their monthly income increases because it is a normal good. The model shows a moderate ability to explain shawarma demand patterns because 20% of the changes in demand result from these factors. The model results show that these factors influence shawarma demand, but other unaccounted factors also affect how people consume shawarma.

Table 4.2 Price and income elasticity of fast-food Consumption

	Coefficient	Mean value	Estimated elasticity
Price	-0.12	608.64	-0.14
Income	0.19	44732.93	15.88

Table 4.2 shows the results of price and income elasticity tests for fast-food consumption to help understand consumer buying behavior. The price elasticity -0.14 shows that fast-food consumption remains stable when prices rise by 1%. Fast food remains popular because it offers both convenience and affordability despite price hikes. The income elasticity of 15.88 shows strong responsiveness because a 1% rise in household income results in a 15.88% boost in fast-food consumption. People who earn more money spend more on fast food because these products offer them a convenient eating option. (Hoffer et al., 2017) concluded that income has a positive and significant impact on fast food consumption. Findings show that fast-food demand depends heavily on

income levels but remains relatively unaffected by price changes, showing that companies should focus their marketing on income groups while setting prices that match what customers can afford.

SUMMARY

Youth worldwide eat more fast food because it saves time and money, while companies target them through marketing. South Asian countries, including Pakistan, are moving away from traditional carbohydrate diets and toward eating more fatty foods with added sugar and salt because of urbanization and rising incomes. Pakistan's fast-food industry is the second-largest food sector and creates jobs while producing food because young people and growing cities embrace fast food as a lifestyle choice. This research examines fast food consumption patterns in Faisalabad, a city experiencing rapid socio-economic development. We use demand theory to study how different consumer groups spend their money based on income and personal preferences. Based on a survey of 150 participants, descriptive statistics and multiple regression analyses were employed to identify key drivers of fast food demand. The findings reveal that younger individuals are the primary consumers, as age negatively correlates with expenditure, suggesting that older individuals have healthier eating habits. Education levels positively influence spending, reflecting greater awareness of food quality and options. Income also has a significant positive impact, with higher-income groups spending more on fast food due to more significant discretionary income. Interestingly, while the variety of fast food options does not significantly affect expenditure, factors such as quality, especially in taste and perceived nutritional value, powerfully drive consumption. In contrast, the physical environment of restaurants has minimal influence, as consumers prioritize food quality and price. Price sensitivity is relatively low, as indicated by an insignificant relationship between price and expenditure, suggesting that fast food demand is price-inelastic. However, income elasticity is notably high, highlighting the critical role of rising incomes in shaping consumption patterns. The demand models for specific fast food items (burgers, pizza, and shawarma) reveal nuanced consumer behavior. Burgers exhibit significant price sensitivity, with complementary and substitutive relationships observed for pizza and shawarma. Pizza demand decreases with higher prices, whereas shawarma shows minimal sensitivity to price changes. Income growth increases demand for all products because they act as standard goods. This research shows that when prices rise by 1%, consumers reduce their purchases by 0.14%, but when their income increases by 1%, they boost their purchases by 15.88%. This research adds important information about fast-food consumption in Faisalabad by filling knowledge gaps in emerging market food habits studies. It shows that growing incomes and changing consumer tastes drive fast-food demand, affecting businesses and healthcare providers who must respond to this trend.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Several policy actions aim to address Faisalabad's growing fast food consumption and related issues. Public health programs must teach people in schools and neighborhoods about fast food dangers through educational efforts. Menus with clear nutritional labels that show calorie content and nutrient information help people choose healthier options. The government should lower prices for nutritious food to make it easier for people to buy it. Taxing processed fast food items would help people eat healthier while generating funds for public health programs. Fast food outlets that serve healthier meals will receive rewards through our program. Lower-income families need income-based programs to buy nutritious food at lower prices and overcome financial barriers to healthy eating.

Marketing rules must block ads that reach children but support honest efforts to help people choose healthier food. Urban planners should restrict fast food outlets from opening near schools and create better access to nutritious food throughout neighborhoods and business districts. The food quality at fast food restaurants can improve when we set stricter nutrition rules and support restaurants that use fresh local ingredients. When customers earn rewards for healthier food options, their behavior changes toward better dietary choices. Research about how people eat fast food and what affects their choices needs to continue to develop effective rules. Schools and workplaces should start nutrition programs by serving nutritious food and organizing wellness activities to help people eat well.

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REFERENCES

1. Al-Khalaifah, H., & Al-Nasser, A. (2022). Importance of poultry industry during global crisis with special reference to covid-19 crisis. *International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference: SGEM*, 22(6.1), 89-96.
2. Akhtar, M. (2013, October 19). Fast Food Industry of Pakistan Growth and History. Retrieved from Pakistan Education News, Universities admission scholarships, and Results website: <https://ilm.com.pk/pakistan/pakistan-information/fast-food-industry-of-pakistan-growth-and-history/>
3. Alviola IV, P. A., Nayga Jr, R. M., Thomsen, M. R., Danforth, D., & Smartt, J. (2014). The effect of fast-food restaurants on childhood obesity: a school level analysis. *Economics & Human Biology*, 12, 110–119.
4. Andreyeva, T., R.I. Kelly, and J.L. Harris. (2011). Exposure to food advertising on television: Associations with children's fast food and soft drink consumption and obesity. *Economics and Human Biology*. 9: 221–233.
5. Baig, A. K and M. Saeed. 2012. Review of trends in fast food consumption. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*. 48: 77-85.
6. Bishwajit, G. (2015). Nutrition transition in South Asia: the emergence of non-communicable chronic diseases. *F1000Research*, 4, 8. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.5732.1>
7. Brunello, G., M.D. Paola and G. Labartino. 2014. More apples fewer chips? The effect of school Fruit schemes on the consumption of junk food. *Journal of Health policy*. 118: 114-126.
8. Chidinma, M. C., Callistus, O. T., & Obi, C. I. (2022). Asymmetric Relationship between Changes in Food Prices and Household Consumption in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 81–89. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2022/v22i213069>
9. Dean, E., Elardo, J., Green, M., Wilson, B., & Berger, S. (2020). Shifts in Demand and Supply for Goods and Services. *Principles of Economics: Scarcity and Social Provisioning (2nd Ed.)*.
10. Fortune Business Insights. (2022). *Fast Food Market Size, Share, Trends & Growth [2021-2028]*. www.fortunebusinessinsights.com. <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/fast-food-market-106482>
11. Franchise Direct. (2020). Rankings of the Top 100 Franchises of 2020 | FranchiseDirect.com. Retrieved from Franchisedirect.com website: <https://www.franchisedirect.com/top100globalfranchises/rankings>
12. Government of Pakistan. (2024). *Pakistan economic survey 2024*. Ministry of Finance. Retrieved from https://www.finance.gov.pk/survey_2024.html
13. Gostkowski, M. (2018). Elastyczność popytu konsumpcyjnego: estymacja na podstawie Quadratic Almost Ideal Demand System. *Ekonometria*, 22(1), 68-78.
14. Hoffer, A., Gvillo, R., Shughart, W., & Thomas, M. (2017). Income-expenditure elasticities of less-healthy consumption goods. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy*, 6(1), 127–148. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jcpp-03-2016-0008>
15. Hong, S. (2019). Comparison of Fast Food Consumption Patterns, Choice, and Satisfaction According to Age. *Journal of the Korea Entertainment Industry Association*, 13(5), 25–36. <https://doi.org/10.21184/jkeia.2019.7.13.5.25>
16. Islam, D. M. R. (2021). Education and Food Consumption Patterns: Quasi-Experimental Evidence from Indonesia. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3925151>
17. Jang, D. and A.S. Mattila. 2005. An examination of restaurant loyalty programs: what kinds of rewards do customers prefer? *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. 17 (5):402-408.
18. Janssen, H. G., Davies, I. G., Richardson, L. D., & Stevenson, L. (2017). Determinants of takeaway and fast food consumption: a narrative review. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 31(1), 16–34. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0954422417000178>
19. Korkmaz, S. 2005. An evaluation of fast food preferences according to gender. *Humanity and Social Sciences*. 2(1):43-50.
20. Lin, B.-H., & Frazao, E. (1997). Nutritional Quality of Foods At and Away From Home. *Food Review: The Magazine of Food Economics*, 20(2), 1–8.
21. Lotfali Agheli, & Emamgholipour, S. (2016). Analyzing Fast Food Consumption Among Iranian Urban Households. *DergiPark (Istanbul University)*.
22. Mathur, S., & Patodiya, P. K. (2016). Global perspective of fast food consumption: a systematic literature review. *Indian Journal of Management Science*, 6(2), 46.

23. Parvin, N. (2022). The Trend of High Consumption of Fast Foods and Its Impact on Families, Individuals, and Societies. *AIJR Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.21467/preprints.389>
24. Payab, M., R. Kelishadi, M. Qorbani, M.E. Motlagh, S.H. Ranjbar, G. Ardalan, H. Zahedi, M. Chinian, H. Asayesh, B. Larijani, R. Heshmat. Alviola. Association of junk food Consumption with high blood pressure and obesity in Iranian children and Adolescents: the CASPIAN-IV Study. 225(1): 1-10.
25. Riaz, F., I. Wahla and Naseem. 2006. Fast food Pakistan. Retrieved online from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/Delivery.cfm/SSRN_ID1856319_code1665125.pdf?abstractid=1856319&mirid=1
26. Rojas, R.M., V.S. Castro, U.C. Ramos, M.C. Aragon and F.H. Raven. 2013. Psychosocial factors influencing the frequency of fast-food consumption among urban and rural costa rican adolescents. *Nutrition*. 29: 1007-1012.
27. Rössel, J. (2015). Education and Consumption. *The Wiley Blackwell Encyclopedia of Consumption and Consumer Studies*, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118989463.wbeccs105>
28. Shaikh, A., M. Rehman. 2010. Determinants of choice for dining out to fast food and traditional food. Research paper. Available online at jisr.szabist.edu.pk/JISR-MSSE/Publication/2010/8/2/1007MSSE09.pdf.
29. Skoufias, E., Di Maro, V., González-Cossío, T., & Ramirez, S. R. (2011). Food quality, calories and household income. *Applied Economics*, 43(28), 4331–4342. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2010.491454>
30. Vachaspati, P. O., Z. Isgor. L. Rimkus., L. M. Powell, D. C. Barker and F. J. Chaloupka. 2015. Child directed marketing inside and on the exterior of fast food restaurant American of journal of preventive medicine. 48(1) 22- 30.
31. Vita, G. D., Salvo, G. D., Bracco, S., Gulisano, G., & D'Amico, M. (2016). Future market of pizza: which attributes do they matter?. *AGRIS on-line Papers in Economics and Informatics*, 8(4), 59-71.
32. Yahya, F., R. Zafar and S. Shafaq. 2013. Trend of fast food consumption and its effect on Pakistani society. *Food Science and Quality Management*. www.iiste.org ISSN 2224-6088 (Paper) ISSN 2225-0557 (Online).11, 2013.
33. Yu, J. H. 2012. Mother's perception of the negative impact on TV food ads on children's food choices. 59: 372-376.
34. Zahedi, H., R. Kelishadi, R. Heshmat, M. E. Motlagh, S. H. Ranjbar, G. Ardalan, M. Payab, M. Chinian, H. Asayesh, B. Larijani and M. Qorbani. 2014. Association between junk food consumption and mental health in a national sample of Iranian children and Adolescents. 30: 1391-1397.

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